

Analysis of Student's Actual – Ideal Competencies in Universitas Negeri Medan in Applying Learning Integrated Guidance Counseling Service in Primary School

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Abstract:- This research aimed to analyze the student's actual-ideal competence level that will be teacher applying the guidance counselling service, especially in SD (Primary School) and TK (Pre-School) accurately through research and to know the level of area content plateauing as well as its correlation with student's actual competencies in applying the guidance counselling services in SD and TK. To reach this goal, was conducted qualitative research to be complement with qualitative narration, by following the research phases as follows: 1. Developing research instrument, 2. Doing instrument validation based on expert judgment and empirically, 3. Collecting and analyzing data, 4. Arranging student's competence development program in applying guidance counselling service in SD and TK based on research results and expert judgment, 5. Arranging the headline of guidance counseling services development module in SD and TK. The research findings showed that (1) Primary School Teacher Education (PSTE) students evaluated their competence in applying learning integrated guidance service in Primary School, holistically owning classified middle, with averagely actual score reach 28,26. Meanwhile, students ideally have competence classified high on the score above 28.00-42.00; (2). study program of Early Age Children Education (EACE) students evaluated their competence in applying learning integrated guidance service in Primary School, holistically classified middle, with averagely actual score reach 27,08. Meanwhile, students ideally having competence classified high were at score reach 28.00-42.00; (3) study program of Guidance Counseling (GC) students in Universitas Negeri Medan evaluated their competence in applying learning integrated guidance service in Primary School, holistically classified high, with actual score reach 40,60. Student's ideal reach, namely classified high, was at competence score reach 28.00-42.00.

Keywords:- Competence, Student, Guidance Counselling Service in SD and TK.

I. INTRODUCTION

Guidance and counselling service in formal education institution Indonesia is part of three integrated formal education system areas, namely, management, learning, and psycho-educative areas. (Menanti et al, 2022). The psycho-educative area doer was implemented by guidance and counselling teacher (GC teachers). The existence of guidance counseling was available in rule of Indonesia Republic Education and Culture Ministry Number 111 Year 2014, article 9, paragraph 1 proposing that guidance counselling service in a education unit was done by counsellor or guidance counselling teacher. Then there are on article 2 ensured that implementation responsibility of guidance counselling service was done by counsellor or guidance counselling teacher. The decision of Indonesia education and culture ministry rule Number 111 Year 2014, article 9, paragraph 1 and 2 ensured that guidance counselling service is part of unseparatable component to bring up learners to become optimal developing individu.

The decision included in rule of MENPAN RB Number 16 Year 2009, article 13, was determined classroom teacher activities as much as 15 items. First item is that classroom teacher assigns to implement guidance and counselling service in classroom. This rule indicated guidance counselling service can be done by classroom teacher (subject teacher), if the existence of professional guidance counselling teacher can not be met yet. Almost all basic educations especially in SD and TK Indonesia did not have professional guidance counselling teacher handling student/children psycho-educative problems, so guidance counselling service was integrated to learning conducted by teacher naturally and not based on accurately concept-theoretic. On the other part, guidance counselling student does not accept guidance counselling subject integrated on education unit in SD or EACE, so there is not enough guarantee they have competence to be guidance counselling teacher in SD and TK. The study program/department graduate that will work in SD or TK needed competence in applying integrated guidance counselling service.

The current research result conducted by Menanti et al (2022) to basic education teacher in Medan Johor district indicated that teacher's competence in applying subject integrated guidance counselling service in SD, holistically is low, and the lowest competence aspect is pedagogical aspect. The low teacher competence applying the integrated guidance counseling service is important to be followed up with some concrete actions, as follows:

- Department/ study program is doing study curriculum adaptation, so as early as possible candidates of preschool and basic education teachers were prepared to be competence ones applying the integrated guidance counseling and guidance counselling teacher candidate could applies professional guidance counselling service in SD and EACE. For this, need to start with research on actual– ideal competence.
- To complete the research proposed on point (1) above researching by involving the most crucial variable influences student's competence achievement in applying the guidance and counseling, namely variable of area content plateauing (Consider job as routine thing) (Milstein & Henderson, 2003).
- Lecturer equips student with more practical and innovative skill and knowledge in guidance counselling service in SD and TK.
- Lecturer was doing research on how to find internal and external factors influencing teacher's competence in applying the learning integrated guidance counselling service done by teacher.

In this opportunity, writer was called to conduct a research on increasing of internal product quality in Universitas Negeri Medan, especially student's quality of PSTE, EACE, GC, with research topic formulation "Analysis of Student's Actual-Ideal Competence in Universitas Negeri Medan in Applying the Learning Integrated Guidance Counseling Service conducted by Teacher".

➤ *Formulation of the Problem*

- How is level of PSTE, EACE, GC student's actual competence in Universitas Negeri Medan in applying guidance counselling service in SD, TK?
- How is level of PSTE, EACE, GC student's ideal competence in Universitas Negeri Medan in applying guidance counselling service in SD, TK?
- How is the gap between PSTE, EACE, GC student's actual and ideal competence levels in Universitas Negeri Medan in applying guidance counselling service in SD, TK?

II. REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

➤ *Concept, Objectives, Functions of Guidance and Counseling*

Surya (1980) meant guidance as contineously and systematically assistance giving process to guide in order to achieve independence in self-understanding, self-acceptance, self-direction, and self-manifestation in achieving the optimal

development level and self-adjustment to an environment. McLeod (2003) proposed counselling as follows:

Counselling includes work with individuals and with relationships which may be developmental, crisis support, psychotherapeutic, guiding or problem solving... The task of counselling is to give the 'client' an opportunity to explore, discover and clarify ways of living more satisfyingly and resourcefully" (BAC, 1984).

- *Then McLeod (2003) told:*

Counselling denotes a professional relationship between a trained counsellor and a client... This relationship is usually person-to-person, although it may sometimes involve more than two people. It is designd to help clients to understand and clarify their views of their lifespaces, and to learn to reach their self-determined goals through meaningful, well-informed choices and through resolution of problems of an emotional or interpersonal nature" (Burks and Stefflre, 1979: 14)

Guidance and counsel was considered as activity that can sustain and stand each in accordance with need. Viewed from its extent, guidance was considered broader than counseling. Nayak (1997: 3) proposed that "guidance is a term which is broader than counselling and which includes counselling as one of its services". Pine and Boy (1968:51) differentiated guidance from counselling in the sides of process, attention centered, group seize, and leader orientation. Guidance is cognitive process, attention to information, goal to increase knowledge, unlimited group seize, and leader orientation is informational. Counseling process is *affective*, attention on person, objective for *self-actualization*, group seize sums *one to eight*, and leader orientation toward *therapeutic*.

Based on expert judgment, researcher concluded that guidance counselling goal is to facilitate so that individual can promote optimal in accordance with intelligence, interest, talent. With the intelligence developing by watching interest direction and individual talent, it can be predicted individual can develop optimal.

Departure from expert judgment, writer summarized that guidance counselling functions to facilitate and to provide insight, direction, and problem solving faced by individual, so individual can finally solve his problem with his potency and life experience independently.

➤ *Subject Integrated Guidance and Counseling Service*

The word, integration in KBBI (2007: 365) was meant as united, combination to be a big and holistic unit; and the word, integrate, was meant integrating, combining, uniting (366). Based on the word of integration, integrating above, so learning integrated guidance counselling service conducted by teacher is guidance counselling service where its application is integrated with activity when teacher is doing the instruction activity.

➤ *Guidance and Counseling Service in Junior/Senior High School, Basic School, and Pre-school Education*

Concept, goal, and function of Guidance Counseling service starting from pre-school education to high school is similar, namely facilitating individual to be able to develop optimal. The difference is placed on application because of development factor, developmental tasks, student's development period characteristic, and guidance counselling service condition was implemented integrated or guidance counselling service was implemented specifically by professional personnel (Menanti et al (2022), (look Murad at all, 2022).

Guidance and Counseling in pre-school has an objective concurrently with its education goal, namely increasing intelligence, knowledge, emotion, social, attitude, skill to live independently, and to follow next study. Guidance counselling service in SD carried on adjustment, orientation,

and developmental functions (Nayak, 1997). The student who is able to adjust himself to family, school and surrounding millieu, obtains guidance and direction and there is any support to facilitate student's psychological development, so it will converges in the optimal development. Paper on Prevention and Elementary School Counselor at Elementary School Guidance and Counseling by Robert L. Gibson (1989) (Gibson and Mitchell (2010) proposed the main function of basic school counsellor was individual counselling functions, group guidance counselling, working with parents, consultation to teacher and administrator, class guidance, assessment, coordination with community institutions.

Guidance counselling service in SD and TK integrated in learning conducted by teacher, but in senior high school it was implemented by professional personnel (Guidance counselling teacher). It can be seen on figure 1 and figure 2.

Fig 1 The Position of Guidance and Counseling in Pre-School

Guidance counselling service in pre-school education is to place on earlier education foundations more than basic school education. The education in pre-school was some building efforts to facilitate the physiologically and psychologically growth and development so that child has readiness in completing the following school (Ariyanti, 2006). The pre-school general goal is to develop child' multi potential as optimal as possible earlier as a plan to face and to

adjust himself to the next life growth and development. The specifically objectives is related to religion education, to develop motoric and physically skills, thinking ability, speaking, art, personal, emotion, and social, and to be conducted by learning stimulation while playing. The existence of Guidance Counseling service in pre-school is figured on figure 3.

Fig 2 Position of Guidance and Counseling in Pre-school Education

Counseling in Pre-school Education integrating above, so learning integrated guidance counselling service conducted by teacher is guidance counselling service where its application is integrated with activity when teacher is doing the instruction activity.

➤ *Research Results that have been done and its Reach*

Informal interview and researcher’s observation to PGSD, PAUD, BK students in applying guidance counselling service in SD and TK indicates less of readiness. It can be seen to be caused by subject sks weight related to Guidance Counseling in SD, TK, but to PSTE and EACE students have small weight (only 2 sks). There is no guidance counselling service subject in SD and pre-school at guidance counselling students, but curriculum focusses on subject of guidance and counselling service in senior high school.

The researcher’s interview results above was parallel with current research findings conducted by Menanti et al (2022) on teacher competence in 15 SD Medan Johor district with total of 130 teachers, who founded that primary school teacher competence in applying integrated guidance counselling service, especially to pedagogical aspect was classified low. The other research done by Menanti et al (2012) to Guidance Counseling students in Universitas Negeri

Medan related to guidance counselling service competence in SD founded that: 1) The average score of actual professional counsellor characteristic was classified middle, 2) The student’s competence interpreting nonverbal language on the initial evaluation was classified middle (58,8%), low (26,66%), and high (14,14%) (Menanti et all, 2015). Researcher’ exploration to the other research on pre-school teacher competence in applying learning integrated guidance counselling service done by teacher, not find it yet.

III. RESEARCH METHOD

This research is research and development (Research & Development), this method was purposed to produce ice breaking module in a valid learning to increase pedagogic stripe student’s academic resilience in Universitas Negeri Medan. Development model was *Four-D Model*, developed by Thiagarajan, purposed to develop, to validate product (Sugiyono, 2018: 407), in form of *ice breaking* module in learning increasing student’s academic resilience.

➤ *Research Phases*

The template is designed so that author affiliations are not repeated each time for multiple authors of the same affiliation.

Fig 3 Research Flow Chart

• *Keterangan:*

P, S, B, K, K, A = Areas of personal development, social, learning. Career, family life, Religion life O, I, PP, K, BKp, K, M, KL = Services of orientation, information, placement and recruitment, Content mastery, group guidance, mediation, consultation, counseling.

Figure 3 showed that less competence PSTE, EACE students is expected after accepting training to be competent student in applying learning integrated guidance counselling service conducted by basic education/pre-school teachers and guidance counselling student will be competence to work as professional guidance counselling teachers in SD, TK. For this, it is needed accurately empirical data through research on actual and ideal PSTE, EACE, GC students competence,

and empirical data on student's area content plateauing in applying guidance counselling service in SD, TK. Based on competence data standard of actual ideal gap covering area and kind of guidance counseling service and data on student's area content plateauing, it is designed a program of student competence development as well as its module head line.

➤ *Identify the Headings*

Headings, or heads, are organizational devices that guide the reader through your paper. There are two types: component heads and text heads.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

➤ *Department of PSTE*

Table 1 Guidance and Counseling Expert's Validation in Guidance and Counseling Material (Academic Resilience)

Number	Competence Aspects	Competence Score Reach and Categorization			
		Actual Competence		Ideal Competences	
		Reach	Category	Reach	Category
1	Comprehension on concepts of guidance counseling base in Primary School	7,37	Middle	08.00-12.00	High
2	Mastery on appropriate guidance service program toward student	6,53	High	05.33-08.00	High
3	Identifying/finding/observing student's behavior phenomenon	3,22	Middle	03.33-05.00	High
4	Ability to perform basic skill to respond students	11,14	Middle	11,34-17.00	High
	Total	28,26	Middle	28-42	High

Table 1 indicated that PSTE students in Universitas Negeri Medan evaluated their competence in applying learning integrated guidance service in Primary School, holistically owning classified middle or at the beginning point classified high, with averagely actual score reach 28,26. Meanwhile, students ideally have competence classified high on the score above 28.00-42.00.

➤ *Department of EACE*

Table 2 Level of PAUD Student's Actual-Ideal Competences in Universitas Negeri Medan in Applying Learning Integrated Guidance Service in Primary School, According to whole Competence Aspect

Number	Competence Aspects	Competence Score Reach and Categorization			
		Actual Competence		Ideal Competences	
		Reach	Category	Reach	Category
1	Comprehension on concepts of guidance counseling base in Primary School	7,35	Middle	08.00-12.00	High
2	Mastery on appropriate guidance service program toward student	5,32	Middle	05.33-08.00	High
3	Identifying/finding/observing student's behavior phenomenon	3,44	High	03.00-05.00	High
4	Ability to perform basic skill to respond students	10,97	Middle	11.34-17.00	High

Table 2 indicated that study program of EACE students evaluated their competence in applying learning integrated guidance service in Primary School, holistically classified middle or to the beginning point classified high, with averagely actual score reach 27,08. Meanwhile, students ideally having competence classified high were at score reach 28.00-42.00.

➤ *Study Program of Guidance Counselling*

Table 3 Level of Guidance Counseling Student's Ideal-Actual Competences in Universitas Negeri Medan in Applying Learning Integrated Guidance Service in Primary School According to Whole Competence Aspect

Number	Competence Aspects	Competence Score Reach and Categorization			
		Actual Competence		Ideal Competences	
		Reach	Category	Reach	Category
1	Comprehension on concepts of guidance counseling base in Primary School	11,75	High	12	High
2	Mastery on appropriate guidance service program toward student	7,71	High	8	High

3	Identifying/finding/observing student’s behavior phenomenon	4,56	High	5	High
4	Ability to perform basic skill to respond students	16,58	High	17	High
	Total	40,60	High	42	High

Table 3 showed that study program of guidance counselling student in Universitas Negeri Medan evaluated their competence in applying learning integrated guidance service in Primary School, holistically classified high, with actual score reach 40,60. Student’s ideal reach, namely classified high, was at competence score reach 28.00-42.00.

Table 4 Student’s Ideal-Actual Competences inn Universitas Negeri Medan in Applying Learning Integrated Guidance Service in Primary School to Aspect of basic Concepts Comprehension of Guidance Service in Primary School

Competence Aspects	Competence Score Reach and Categorization				Average of Actual Competence	Score and Ideal Competence Categorization
	Actual Competence		Ideal Competences			
	Reach	Category	Reach	Category		
Comprehension on basic concepts of guidance and counseling services in Primary School	11,75	High	12	High	8,82	Comprehension on basic concepts of guidance and counseling services in Primary School

Table 4 showed that student’s actual competence in faculty of education (average study programs of PSTE, EACE, GC students) in applying learning integrated guidance service in Primary School to aspect of basic concepts comprehension of Guidance Counseling service in Primary School, classified high, with average score reach 8.82.

Table 5 Student’s Ideal-Actual Competences in Universitas Negeri Medan in Applying Learning Integrated Guidance Service in Primary School to Aspect of basic Concepts Comprehension of Guidance Service in Primary School

Competence Aspects	Score reach and Student’s Actual Competence Categorization in Universitas Negeri Medan				Score and Ideal Competence Categorization
	Students of PGSD	Students of PAUD	Students of BK	Average	
Appropriate Guidance Service Area Performed by Teacher toward basic school students	6,53 High	5,32 Middle	7,71 High	6,52 High	05.33-08.00

Table 5. showed that Student’s actual competence in Universitas Negeri Medan (average students of PSTE, EACE, GC study programs) in applying learning integrated guidance service in Primary School to aspect of guidance service appropriately performed by teacher toward basic school students, classified high, with average score reach 6.52.

Table 6 FIP Student’s Ideal-Actual Competences in Universitas Negeri Medan in Applying Learning Integrated Guidance Service in Primary School to Aspect of Ability to Identify/to Find/to Observe basic School Student’s Behavior

Competence Aspects	Score reach and Student’s Actual Competence Categorization in Universitas Negeri Medan				Score and Ideal Competence Categorization
	PGSD Students	PAUD students	BK Students	Average	
Ability to identify/to find/to observe basic school student’s behaviors	3,22 Middle	3,44 High	4,56 High	3,74 High/ Middle+	03.00-05.00

Table 6. showed that Faculty of Education student’s actual competence in Universitas Negeri Medan (average student of PSTE, EACE, GC study programs) in applying learning integrated guidance service in Primary School to aspect of ability to identify/to find/to observe basic school student’s behaviors, classified high, with actual competence score reach 03.74.

Table 7 FIP Student’s Ideal-Actual Competences in Universitas Negeri Medan in Applying Learning Integrated Guidance Service in Primary School to Aspect of Ability to Perform basic Skills in Responding Students

Competence Aspects	Score reach and Student’s Actual Competence Categorization in Universitas Negeri Medan				Score and Ideal Competence Categorization
	PGSD Students	PAUD students	BK Students	Average	
Ability to Perform Basic Skills in Responding Students	11,14 Middle	10,97 Middle	16,58 High	10,23 Middle	11,34-17,00

Table 7 showed that student’s actual competence (average students of PSTE, EACE, GC study programs) in Universitas Negeri Medan in applying learning integrated guidance service in Primary School to aspect of ability to perform basic skills in responding students, classified middle, with actual competence score reach 10.23. But ideal competence reach was at score 11.34-17.00.

Table 8 Student’s Ideal-Actual Competences in Universitas Negeri Medan in Applying Learning Integrated Guidance Service in Primary School, Based on whole Competence Aspect and Based on whole Competence Aspect to each Departments/Study Programs

Competence Aspects	Score reach and Student’s Actual Competence Categorization in Universitas Negeri Medan				Score and Ideal Competence Categorization
	PGSD Students	PAUDStudents	BK Students	Average	
Whole total (Competence aspect 1 to 4), namely competence aspect: 1. Teacher’s comprehension on basic concepts in guidance and counseling service in primary school 2. Teacher’s mastery on appropriate guidance service area done to students 3. Identifying/finding/ observing student’s behavior phenomenon 4. Ability to perform basic skills in responding students	28,26 Middle+	27,08 Middle	40,60 High	31,98 High	28.00-42.00 High

Tabel 8 showed that student’s actual competence in Universitas Negeri Medan (average students of PSTE, EACE, GC study programs) in applying learning integrated guidance service in Primary School to whole competence aspect (4 aspects), classified high, with actual competence score reach 31,98.

V. DISCUSSION

Research result showed that discussion about student’s evaluation on their competence in applying learning integrated guidance service covering: 1) discussion based on student’s competence holistically, namely Faculty of Education students in Universitas Negeri Medan (study programs of PSTE, EACE, GC), 2) Discussion based on each study programs/departments), and discussion based on each competence aspect to apply learning integrated guidance service in Primary School. Research results were classified on high, middle, and low competences in applying learning integrated guidance service in Primary School. At the competence classified high, it will be follow up by prevention efforts and keep going, but at the competences classified middle and low, it will be follow up with curative efforts, with high priority scale on competence classified low..

Reinforcement, student’s competence improvement as educator candidate that will plays role as educator (besides subject teacher) in applying learning integrated guidance service in Primary School, Pre-school can be done by the following concepts: (1) Appearing awareness for students the importance of their competences fulfilling professional teacher standard who have responsible for playing role self as subject teacher and as educator manifested into student’s psychologically guiding skill, in whatever education level, like in Primary School. As well as teachers in pre-school. In the meantime, for students who has background of guidance and counselling science in time of working as guidance counselling teacher in Primary School or in pre-school, so

playing role at least if not teaching in the classroom, then being coordinator, programmer, and guidance and counselling service doer by him selves and by subject teacher, (2) Teacher often develops self continuously through a variety of learning resources inside and outside school, (3) Education Institution and Pedagogic Personnel party, in this sense is purposed as manager of study program, department, faculty of education in Universitas Negeri Medan, to adjust curriculum in order to maximize student’s competence in applying learning integrated guidance service.

This following was proposed comprehension on research results related to categorization and follow up research result. Research result displayed by on table 8 about Faculty of Education student’s ideal-actual competences in applying learning integrated guidance service in Primary School to whole competence aspects (4 competence aspects) and whole study programs (PSTE, EACE, GC) showed that student’s competence was at the average score 31,98 classified high or can be told classified above middle as well. Ideal competence achievement is at average score 28.00 – 42.00. With this competence, FIP students in Universitas Negeri Medan holistically in competence aspects and in a whole study programs (PSTE, EACE, GC), needed efforts to maintain and to develop competence better again as well.

The need to develop competence is reinforced by competence profile on each study programs/departments, as follows: At students of PSTE study program displayed on table 1. showed that PSTE students needed reinforcement primarily to competences aspect 1,3,4, but to aspect 2, needed competence maintaining efforts that has been already good. Aspect 1 achieves average score as much as 7,37 classified middle, of average score high competence 12,00. Aspect 3 achieves average score as much as 3,22 classified middle, of average score high/ideal competence 5.00, andn aspect 4 achieves average score 11,14 classified middle, of average score high/ideal competence 17.00. But aspect 2 achieves

average score as much as 6,53 classified high, of average score high/ideal competence 08.00. Holistically (4 competence aspects), PSTE department achieves average score 28,26, classified middle, of achievement of average score ideal competence 28.00 – 42.00.

It is necessary to propose back that aspect 1 of competence is teacher's comprehension on basic concepts in guidance service in Primary School, aspect 2 is teacher's mastery on appropriate guidance service area toward students, aspect 3 is about ability to identify/to find/to observe student's behavior phenomenon, and aspect 4 is ability to perform basic skills of guidance and counselling in responding students.

To students of PSTE department, it was displayed on the table 2 showed that students of EACE department needed reinforcement primarily to competence aspect 1, 2, 4, but to aspect 3, needed competence maintenance that already good. Aspect 1 achieved average score as much as 7.37 classified middle, of average score high competence 12.00. Aspect 2 achieved average score as much as 5,32 classified middle, of average score high competence 8.00, and aspect 4 achieved average score as much as 10,97 classified middle, of high competence score average 17.00. But aspect 3 achieved average score as much as 3,44 classified high, of average score high competence 05.00, needed reach maintenance efforts that has been considered good. Holistically (4 competence aspects), department of EACE achieved average score as much as 20.08, classified middle, of ideal competence reach, average score 28.00 – 42.00.

At study program of GC, displayed on table 3, whole competence aspects averagely were classified good, thus they needed maintenance so that competence did not decrease, even to be better. Aspect 1 achieved average score as much as 11.75 classified high, of average score ideal competence 12.00, aspect 2 achieved average score as much as 7,71 classified middle, of average score ideal competence 8.00, aspect 3 achieved average score as much as 4,56 classified high, of average score ideal competence 5.00, and aspect 4 achieves average score as much as 16,58 classified high, of ideal competence average score 17.00. Holistically (4 competence aspects), BK department achieves average score as much as 40.60, classified high, of ideal competence reach average score 28.00 – 42.00.

The need to develop competence was reinforced by competence profile of whole students in Universitas Negeri Medan (PSTE, EACE, GC) viewed from each competence aspects, as follows: especially to aspect 1, displayed on table 5.8 to need competence reinforcement primarily to departments of PSTE and EACE, but GC study program needed competence maintenance that has been already good. Aspect 1 to PSTE department achieves average score as much as 7,37 classified middle, EACE department achieves average score as much as 7,35 classified middle, but GC study program achieves average score 8,82 classified high. Holistically (PSTE, EACE, GC) average score achieves 8.82, classified middle. This first competence aspect is at the category classified high (ideal) average score 8-12.00.

On aspect 2, displayed on table 2 needed competence reinforcement to students of PSTE department, but students of PSTE and students of GC departments needed competence maintenance that has been already good. This second aspect to students of PSTE department achieves average score as much as 5,35 classified middle, students of PSTE department achieves average score as much as 6,53 classified middle, and GC study program achieves average score as much as 7,71 classified high. Holistically (PSTE, EACE, GC) average score achieves as much as 6.52 classified high. Second competence aspect classified high (ideal) was at average score 5.33 – 8.00.

On third competence aspect, displayed on table 5.10 needed competence reinforcement to students of PSTE department, but students of PSTE department and of GC department needed maintenance competence that has been already good. This third competence aspect to students of PSTE department achieves average score as much as 3.22 classified middle, students of EACE department achieves average score as much as 3,44 classified high, and students of GC study program achieves average score as much as 4,56 classified high. Holistically Faculty of Education students in Universitas Negeri Medan (PSTE, EACE, GC) averagely achieves average score as much as 3.74, classified high. Third competence aspect of high category (ideal) was at average score 3.33 – 5.00.

At fourth competence aspect, displayed on table 7 needed competence reinforcement to students of PSTE and EACE, but students of GC study program needed competence maintenance that has been already good. Aspect 4 to students of PSTE department achieves average score as much as 11,14 classified middle, students of EACE department achieves average score as much as 10,97 classified middle, and students of GC study program achieves average score as much as 16,58 classified high. Holistically students in Universitas Negeri Medan (PSTE, EACE, GC) averagely achieved average score as much as 10.23 classified middle. The fourth competence aspect of ideal/high category was average score 11.34 – 17.00.

VI. CONCLUSION

➤ *Level of Student's Ideal-Actual Competences in Universitas Negeri Medan in Applying Learning Integrated Guidance Service in Primary School:*

Whole student's competence level in Universitas Negeri Medan in applying learning integrated guidance service in Primary School. They evaluated themselves averagely classified high, with score reach 31.98. Ideal score reach was classified high on achievement 28.00 – 42.00, with profile that to students of PSTE department averagely students evaluated their competence classified high with score reach 28.26. Actual score reach was classified high to achievement 28.00 – 42.00. To students of EACE department averagely students evaluated their competence classified middle or at the beginning point classified high, with score reach 27.08. Ideal score reach was classified high on the achievement 28.00 - 42.00. To students of GC department, students averagely evaluated their competence classified high, with score reach

40.60. Ideal score reach was classified high on the achievement 28.00 - 42.00.

➤ *Aspect Profile of Student's Ideal-Actual Competence in Universitas Negeri Medan (PSTE, EACE, GC) in Applying Learning Integrated Guidance Service in Primary School:*

- On competence aspect 1, namely comprehension on basic concept of guidance service in Primary School, students evaluated averagely to classify on high, with average score reach 8.82. Ideal score reach was classified high to achievement 08.00 – 12.00.
- On competence aspect 2, namely appropriate guidance service conducted by teacher to basic school students, averagely students in Universitas Negeri Medan was classified high, with average score reach 6,52. Ideal score reach was classified high to achievement 05.33 - 08.00.
- On competence aspect 3, namely ability to identify/to find/to observe student's behaviors in Primary School, students averagely was classified high in Universitas Negeri Medan, with actual competence score reach 03.74. Ideal score reach was classified high on achievement 03.33 – 05.00.
- On competence aspect 4, namely learning integrated guidance service in Primary School to ability aspect to perform basic skills in responding students, students averagely was classified high in Universitas Negeri Medan, with average score reach 10,23. Ideal score reach was classified high to achievement 11.34 - 17.00.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Ariyanti, T. (2006). Pentingnya Pendidikan AUD bagi Tumbuh kembang Anak. *Dinamika Pendidikan Dasar. Jurnal. Hlm. 50-58. Volume 8, Nomor 1. Diakses Tanggal 8 Januari 2023.*
- [2]. Buku Pedoman Universitas Negeri Medan Tahun (2019). Medan: Universitas Negeri Medan.
- [3]. Gibson, R. L. & Mitchell, M. H. (1995). *Introduction to Counselling and Guidance*. New Jersey: Merrill, an Imprint of Prentice Hall.
- [4]. Henderson, N. & Milstein, M. M. (2003). *Resiliency in School: Making It Happen for Students and Educators*. California: Corwin Press, Inc.
- [5]. McLeod, J. (2003). *An Introduction Counselling*. Buckingham: Open University Press.
- [6]. Menanti, A., dan Kawan-Kawan, (2022). *Kompetensi Guru SD dalam Menerapkan Layanan Bimbingan dan Konseling Terintegrasi Mata Pelajaran, Dianalisis dari Resiliensi dan Locus Kontrol Internal, Kepemimpinan Kepala Sekolah serta Organizational Citizenship Behavior Rekan Kerja di lingkungan Medan Johor. Laporan Penelitian*. Medan: Universitas Negeri Medan.
- [7]. ----- (2022). *Bimbingan dan Konseling di Sekolah Dasar*. Medan: FBS Unimed Press.
- [8]. ----- (2015). *Karakter Konselor Profesional Aktual dan Ideal Mahasiswa Prodi Bimbingan dan Konseling FIP UNIMED Berbasis Standarisasi Pakar*. Medan: Universitas Negeri Medan.
- [9]. ----- (2012). *Meningkatkan Kemampuan Mahasiswa dalam Memaknai Bahasan Nonverbal sebagai Integrasi MKK Melalui Implementasi Pembelajaran Pengalaman Langsung yang Membangun Karakter Self Control*. Medan: Universitas Negeri Medan.
- [10]. Murad, A., et al. (2022). *The Basic Teacher Competence in Applying Subject Integrated Guidance and Counseling Viewed from Work Colleague's Control Locus and Resilience*. *International Journal of Innovative Science and Research Technology. IJRST A Digital Library. IVolume 7, Issue 10, ISSN No:-256-2165. Diakses Tanggal 9 Januari 2023.*
- [11]. Nayak, A. K. 1997. *Guidance and Counselling*. New Delhi: APH Publishing Corporation.
- [12]. *Pedoman Akademik Universitas Negeri Medan (2019)*. Medan: Universitas Negeri Medan.
- [13]. *Peraturan Menteri Pendidikan dan Budaya RI Nomor 111 Tahun 2014 tentang Bimbingan dan Konseling pada Pendidikan Dasar dan Pendidikan Menengah*.
- [14]. *Peraturan Menteri Negara Pendayagunaan Aparatur Negara dan Reformasi Birokrasi Nomor 16 tahun 2019*.
- [15]. Prayitno. (2004). *Layanan Informasi*. Padang: Jurusan Bimbingan dan Konseling Fakultas Ilmu Pendidikan Universitas Negeri Padang.
- [16]. Surya, M. (1988). *Dasar-Dasar Penyuluhan (Konseling)*. Jakarta: Departemen P dan K Dirjen Dikti PPLPTK.